

Cardiometabolic Risk in Adolescent Polycystic Ovary Syndrome: Bridging Endocrinology, Gynecology, and Preventive Cardiology

Authors:

Saba Ryadh Younis al-Obaidi¹, Abdulameer Jasim Jawad al-Gburi², Wasnaa Hadi Abdullah³

¹MBChB, CABOG, Gynecologist, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, College of Medicine, al-Nahrain University, Baghdad, Iraq.

²MBChB, ABHS (Med), FIBMS (Med), FIBMS (Cardio), Cardiologist, Department of Medicine, College of Medicine, Mustansiriya University, Baghdad, Iraq.

³MBChB, ABHS (Ped), FIBMS (Ped Endo), Pediatric Endocrinologist, Department of Pediatrics, College of Medicine, Mustansiriya University, Baghdad, Iraq.

Corresponding Author:

Abdulameer Jasim Jawad al-Gburi, MBChB, ABHS (Med), FIBMS (Med), FIBMS (Cardio), Cardiologist, Department of Medicine, College of Medicine, Mustansiriya University, Baghdad, Iraq.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19394517>

Received: 01-March-2026, Revised: 16-March-2026, Accepted: 01-April-2026, Online First: 03-April-2026

ABSTRACT:

Background: Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is one of the most common endocrine disorders in adolescents, affecting around 6-10% of the global population. While previously considered a reproductive and gynecological disorder, PCOS is now viewed as a chronic, multisystemic metabolic and cardiovascular disorder that begins in early life and continues throughout adulthood. **Objective:** This study intended to summarize opportunities created by combining pediatric endocrinology, pediatric gynecology, and preventive cardiology to identify and risk stratify for subclinical cardiovascular dysfunction in early adolescence, an important developmental and pubertal transition period. **Methods:** This is a qualitative review of the contemporary literature, including primary research, meta-analyses, and clinical practice guidelines on adolescent PCOS, adipose tissue dysfunction, and advanced cardiovascular imaging. **Discussion:** The most important endocrine abnormality in PCOS is marked insulin resistance and associated compensatory hyperinsulinemia. Thus, the metabolic disturbances and adverse adipokine profile in "Lean PCOS" phenotypes indicate that severe cardiometabolic risk exists beyond simply that of common clinical obesity. Cardiovascular dysfunction associated with the metabolic syndrome occurs in youth, with PCOS adolescents already showing increased arterial stiffness, subclinical atherosclerosis, and early vascular ageing. Important deposition of massive epicardial adipose tissue (EAT) is also seen. EAT is a metabolically active visceral fat depot with pro-inflammatory, metabolically harmful properties that directly affect coronary and myocardial dysfunction. Due to preserved ejection fraction in early stage disease, advanced imaging, including speckle tracking echocardiography, is often required to assess mechanical impairment of the heart. These abnormalities include impaired left ventricular global longitudinal strain, subclinical right ventricular dysfunction, and complex biventricular mechanical dispersion. **Conclusion:** Effective prevention of premature cardiovascular disease in adolescent PCOS requires the transition from symptom-based, fragmented care to multidisciplinary cardio-metabolic-gynecologic clinics, and standardized advanced imaging protocols along with rigorous cardiovascular and metabolic screening. With these tools, it is possible to change the lifelong cardiovascular trajectory of this high-risk population.

Keywords: Polycystic ovary syndrome, adolescents, insulin resistance, adiposity.

INTRODUCTION:

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is the most common endocrine disorder affecting women, with a worldwide prevalence of 6% to 10% in female adolescents and 10% to 13% in adult women.^{1,2} The diagnosis of PCOS was originally within the scope of

gynecology and reproductive endocrinology, and is characterized by chronic anovulation, hyperandrogenism, and infertility.³ Unlike in the past, modern medicine recognizes PCOS as more than a reproductive disorder but a lifelong and multisystem

metabolic and cardiovascular disease, warranting early diagnosis and monitoring.⁴

The pathophysiological metabolic defects of PCOS related to severe insulin resistance, compensatory hyperinsulinemia, and chronic low-grade inflammation are now considered to be early triggering factors in the progression of metabolic syndrome itself.⁵ The systemic consequences of the intrinsic metabolic abnormalities in women with PCOS carry a lifetime risk of developing the major comorbidities associated with PCOS, including type 2 diabetes mellitus, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD), obstructive sleep apnea, and premature atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (CVD).⁶

It would be especially meaningful to stress that the cardiovascular and metabolic phenomena relevant to PCOS do not emerge in adulthood, but have a very clear pathophysiological origin in youth, whereby physiological insulin resistance can be pathologically exaggerated by excess androgens and/or by dysfunction of the adipose tissue.⁷ Emerging evidence suggests that early vascular aging in adolescent girls with PCOS is present via subclinical atherosclerosis, increased carotid intima-media thickness and arterial stiffness when compared with healthy controls.⁸ Silent heart remodeling such as preclinical left ventricular diastolic dysfunction also occurs in adolescent girls with PCOS and is a subclinical marker of future coronary artery disease and heart failure in young women with PCOS.^{9, 10}

In view of the long-term burden of these morbidities, a medical approach towards adolescent girls with clinical signs of ill health is not enough. The present review attempts to unite pediatric endocrinology, gynecology and preventive cardiology to highlight a therapeutic window of opportunity in adolescence when detection and prevention of subclinical cardiovascular dysfunction would be possible. This review highlights that adolescent PCOS is a core cardiometabolic risk factor, and stresses the need for multidisciplinary screening and intervention to modify the CVD trajectory in young women.

The Gynecological Presentation: Defining the Adolescent Phenotype:

Its diagnosis in adolescent girls is difficult, as there is considerable overlap between the physiological disturbances and clinical features of normal puberty and those seen with PCOS. Anovulatory cycles and irregular menstruation are common in normal puberty, as the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian (HPO) axis that regulates menstruation and ovulation matures.¹¹ In adolescence, the typical cutaneous symptoms of hyperandrogenism considered diagnostic of the condition in adult women are less specific. Acne vulgaris is universal during puberty, and the appearance of sexual hair is still in the process of physiological maturation.¹²⁻¹⁴ For this reason, international consensus

guidelines recommend that symptoms of PCOS in girls be categorized as "at risk for PCOS" until menstrual irregularities persist for one or two years post menarche, in order to prevent labeling transient pubertal immaturity as a lifelong disease.^{12, 15}

In view of very high background rates of physiological anovulation, objective evidence of hyperandrogenism is the absolute foundation of a definitive diagnosis of adolescent PCOS.^{12, 16, 13} Clinically the diagnosis of hyperandrogenism is made on the basis of moderate to severe hirsutism (based on Ferriman-Gallwey scoring system) or moderate to severe inflammatory acne resistant to conventional topical dermatological therapy.^{17, 18} Biochemically, diagnosis is based on the presence of hyperandrogenemia that is persistent. Serum free or total testosterone elevation is the most sensitive biochemical marker of the condition, and its measurement depends on the assay method used.^{17, 19, 20} Direct automated assays are not very accurate at low testosterone levels in women and high-quality specialty reference assays are required in such cases, for example liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS).^{21, 22}

Combined oral contraceptives (COCs) are the first-line choice of pharmacologic therapy for management of the gynecological and dermatological manifestations, and should be initiated as soon as a diagnosis is confirmed or presumed.^{23, 2, 14} COCs are thought to exert multifactorial therapeutic actions by suppressing the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian (HPO) axis, providing progestin to oppose endometrial hyperplasia resulting from the chronic anovulatory state, and reducing the bioavailable androgens levels by increasing hepatic production of SHBG and decreasing ovarian testosterone production.^{17, 24}

COCs have many clinical disadvantages. They prevent progression of hirsutism and regulate menstrual periodicity, but mask hyperandrogenemia, which is the cause of symptoms; if it was not measured from the start, it makes reassessment impossible in some cases.²⁵ After the reproductive phenotype is treated, there is the issue of COC formulation, often 30 to 35 mcg ethinyl estradiol, as this cannot adequately control the heavy bleeding or prevent the abnormally high bone mass.^{26, 27} To add to the complexity, the increasing prevalence of obesity and the MS in adolescents must be considered, because additional cardiovascular risk factors must be weighed against the cycle control provided by the COC. Side effects can include hepatic effects and increased risk of venous thromboembolism and lipid derangements.²⁸

The Endocrine Driver: Insulin Resistance and Early Metabolic Syndrome:

Although PCOS diagnosis is often made on gynecological symptoms, the fundamental defect in most PCOS cases is severe insulin resistance and compensatory hyperinsulinemia. In PCOS, insulin resistance is very tissue-specific. Skeletal muscle and

liver are insulin-resistant tissues that normally respond to insulin by taking up glucose, but the ovary is exquisitely sensitive to insulin.^{29, 30} Hyperinsulinemia is a strong co-gonadotropin in the ovary. Furthermore, insulin potentiates the action of LH on theca cells resulting in the LH-dependent hyperstimulation, augments the cytochrome P450c17 enzyme activity, and results in marked ovarian hyperandrogenism.^{31, 32} In addition to this, insulin interacts with local androgens and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) to cause premature luteinization of granulosa cells, producing the classical follicular arrest in the polycystic ovary.^{33, 34}

This dysfunctional adipogenesis and hyperandrogenic and hyperinsulinemic state progresses to early development of metabolic syndrome. In the adolescent PCOS population, excess androgens upregulate the expression of beta-adrenergic receptors in visceral adipose tissue, promoting central adiposity, free fatty acid release, and hepatic gluconeogenesis.^{35, 36} The dysregulated adipose tissue cannot expand appropriately, leading to hypertrophic changes in the adipocytes, impaired adipogenesis, as well as secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines like tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF-alpha).²⁹⁻³¹ Another major alteration is the imbalance of adipokines, characterized by reduced levels of insulin-sensitizing adiponectin and increased levels of leptin.³⁷⁻³⁹

Importantly, there are severe metabolic and adipose abnormalities consistent with PCOS in adolescents who do not have clinical obesity, that is, in "Lean PCOS" adolescents (defined as BMI <85th percentile), who carry high intrinsic metabolic risk. In a population-based longitudinal cohort, lean adolescents with PCOS had considerably higher HOMA-IR levels than normal weight adolescents with similar body mass index (BMI) and considerably lower adiponectin leptin ratios.⁴⁰ The adiponectin leptin ratio is a highly sensitive functional biomarker of the degree of adipose tissue inflammation and cardiometabolic risk. Thus, even in the absence of excess body weight, adolescents with PCOS have important adipose tissue dysfunction and an adverse cardiometabolic biomarker profile.⁴¹

The primary metabolic defect of the syndrome is insulin resistance. Therefore, early metabolic therapy is essential to prevent progression to type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular disease. Multicomponent lifestyle changes, which may include structured physical activity, dietary interventions, and behavioral therapy, are universally recommended first-line therapy for improving body composition and metabolic risk factors.⁴²⁻⁴⁴

If lifestyle changes alone are not successful, treatment with pharmacotherapy such as metformin may be considered if there is impaired glucose tolerance or marked insulin resistance.^{14, 45, 46} Metformin targets the pathophysiology of the disease by suppressing the hepatic production of glucose. This, in turn, controls the hyperinsulinemia associated with the compensatory

excess in insulin secretion.⁴⁷⁻⁵¹ In addition to its insulin sensitizing effects, metformin has been shown to have modestly reduced ovarian androgen production (~20% decrease) at therapeutic doses, with the additional benefit of restoration of ovulation.⁵²⁻⁵⁵ For this reason, early intervention with metabolic treatment during adolescence is also important in order to interrupt the vicious cycle between insulin resistance and hyperandrogenism, prior to irreversible cardiometabolic derangement.

The Cardiovascular Toll: Detecting Subclinical Dysfunction:

With the recognition of adolescent PCOS as a chronic cardiometabolic disorder, the early development of cardiovascular morbidities has become an important area of study. Although the presence of overt cardiovascular disease is rare in youth, the comorbidities of hyperandrogenism and insulin resistance in PCOS result in the establishment of subclinical structural and functional cardiovascular abnormalities.

A) Vascular Aging The early signs of cardiovascular disease in adolescent females with PCOS can be found at the level of the vasculature with precursors of subclinical atherosclerosis (increased cIMT, arterial stiffness) appearing early on in girls with PCOS.⁸ This early vascular aging can be driven by hyperinsulinemia, hypertension, and chronic low-grade inflammation which mediates endothelial dysfunction via impaired nitric oxide-mediated vasodilation and promotes vascular smooth muscle cell hypertrophy in the arterial wall.⁵⁶ It has been shown on echocardiography and vascular ultrasounds that young women with PCOS have a considerably higher specialized measure of carotid artery stiffness (beta stiffness index) and considerably lower carotid artery compliance compared to matched control women.⁵⁷ Central arterial stiffness is a primary, detectable harbinger of advancing vascular age in these young patients.⁵⁸

B) Epicardial Adiposity Epicardial adipose tissue (EAT) is a visceral fat depot located between the myocardium and the visceral epicardium, and is a metabolically active, highly insulin-resistant endocrine organ.⁵⁹ Morphological and functional studies show that lipolysis and release of free fatty acids from EAT is much greater than in other visceral fat depots.⁶⁰ EAT volume can be simply quantified by transthoracic echocardiography by measuring the thickness of the EAT measured on the free wall of the right ventricle.⁶¹ In PCOS, women have a higher echocardiographic EAT thickness, independent of BMI, that correlates positively with serum triglyceride and luteinizing hormone, and this increased thickness is a source of local pro-inflammatory cytokines.⁶² The coronary and myocardial dysfunctions in conjunction increase the inflammatory load, eventually inducing premature atherosclerosis in the premenopausal women of these reproductive age groups.^{59, 63}

C) Myocardial Mechanics Conventional echocardiographic parameters, like left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF), are poor indicators of early cardiac remodeling in adolescent PCOS, as seen in the large-scale meta-analyses. In these analyzes, LVEF was maintained in the majority of studies, with no statistically meaningful differences found, indicating that LVEF is insufficient to indicate early changes in cardiac function.⁶⁴

In contrast to this, preclinical myocardial involvement may be detected with speckle tracking echocardiography (STE) using global longitudinal strain (GLS), a sensitive marker of subclinical LV dysfunction. In PCOS, worse GLS correlates negatively with fasting insulin, insulin resistance (using HOMA-IR) and diastolic filling times.⁶⁵

Additionally, subclinical RV dysfunction, biventricular mechanical dispersion, and impaired RV-PA coupling have been found, in addition to pulmonary arterial stiffness, by echocardiography as potential indicators of cardiovascular risk in women with PCOS.⁶⁶ Besides mechanical, electrical dispersion and electromechanical coupling have occurred, assessed by prolonged atrial electromechanical conduction delay^{67, 68} and increased QT and P-wave dispersion.^{69, 70} Deep electromechanical remodeling has already occurred, undetected, in youth with PCOS. Advanced imaging may improve cardiovascular risk assessment and stratification over a lifetime.

Multidisciplinary Clinical Integration and Future Directions:

Customarily, adolescent PCOS has been managed separately by gynecologic, dermatologic, and endocrine physicians, diagnosing and treating exclusively the menstrual, dermatologic, and metabolic features of the disorder respectively. As PCOS is a chronic, multisystem disorder, management may require a change to cardio-metabolic-gynecologic clinics to ensure appropriate care for women with PCOS across the life span. These multidisciplinary care models are important to delivering a lifelong approach that combines age-appropriate education, preventive intervention, and smooth transfer to adult specialist care.⁷¹ Such an approach would enable clinicians to address the concurrent triad of hyperandrogenism, severe insulin resistance, and precocious adipose tissue dysfunction much earlier in life, and before irreversible cardiovascular damage has occurred.

Cardiometabolic risk in adolescent PCOS parallels other endocrine disorders such as Turner syndrome and subclinical hypothyroidism, where hormonal and genetic factors drive vascular and metabolic dysfunction. Both conditions contribute to insulin resistance, dyslipidemia, and endothelial impairment, increasing cardiovascular risk. Collectively, they emphasize that even subtle endocrine disturbances can promote early atherosclerosis, highlighting the need for timely cardiometabolic screening in PCOS.^{72, 73} A

foundation of this approach is regular and standardized metabolic screening. The 75-g oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) is the first choice for screening as fasting glucose is an insensitive way to identify early impairment of glucose metabolism. The OGTT test should be performed at diagnosis, and repeated every one to three years of follow-up, depending on other risk factors.^{74-76, 2} A baseline lipid panel, annual blood pressure monitoring, and serum alanine aminotransferase (ALT) are also recommended at diagnosis to screen for MASLD (formerly known as NAFLD), regardless of the adolescent's BMI category.²

The prophylactic cardiovascular approach should also include standardized non-intrusive cardiovascular imaging in young women with PCOS. Based on the proposed guidelines, the standardized application of transthoracic echocardiography can be an easily applicable and a reliable tool to quantify EAT and to ascertain the premature cardiovascular risk factor in young PCOS patients. Echocardiographic EAT measurement is a low-cost, widely available, non-ionizing alternative to MRI or CT, and allows for detection of time-sensitive, metabolically toxic visceral adiposity early in cardiometabolic disease.^{59, 77}

In addition to EF, studies utilizing speckle tracking echocardiography (STE) have demonstrated utility in uncovering preclinical myocardial impairment, through impaired global longitudinal strain (GLS), and electromechanical conduction delay in the atria, which are sensitive to subclinical biventricular and electromechanical remodeling far earlier than overt macroscopic dysfunction would otherwise occur.^{67, 65} The incorporation of these ultra-sensitive imaging investigations into a thorough multi-specialty clinical pathway should allow us to move from a reactive symptoms-based approach toward a consistent lifelong cardiovascular prevention strategy for adolescents with PCOS.

Funding sources:

None

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